

ECG Signal Using Time Domain Analysis for Health Care**Shinde Ganesh Madhukar & Gaikwad Pradeep Devendra***R.B. Attal Arts, Science and Commerce College, Georai, Dist. Beed.**Corresponding Author – Gaikwad Pradeep Devendra*

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Abstract:

Focuses solely on Intensive Care Units (ICUs), as it was done on this study, Rapid breathing and heart rate, along with confusion and disorientation are conditions that can be detected by monitoring devices Electric Cardiogram ECG devices. Time domain features will be explored to analyze the periodic functioning of the heart, clinicians examine the beat-to-beat behavior of the heart. were developed to allow the extraction of these features to help medical patients in ICU by foreseeing the deterioration in their health status such as Heart Rate,

Keywords: Signal Processing, ECG, Time Domain Analysis, Health Care.**Introduction:**

The electrocardiogram represents an electrical tracing of the heart and is recorded non-invasively from the surface of the body [1]

Fig. 1. ECG morphology: different segments of ECG signal for normal person

Electrocardiography ECG precisely record the electrical activity of heart rhythm over a period using electrodes/leads, which captures the electrical changes caused by depolarization and re-polarization of heart muscles during heartbeat [2]. This section includes recording of ECG signal by standard 12-conventional leads, noises associated during ECG acquisition, morphology (structural & physiological), and identification of heart related diseases from ECG.

[3]. The electrocardiogram (ECG) is a non-invasive tool used to assess the electrical activity of the heart. . Time domain analysis of ECG signals is one of the most accessible and computationally efficient techniques for analysing heart activity, {[4-7] The Objectives to focus on methods of time-domain analysis and approaches to optimal data collection to ensure high signal quality and diagnostic accuracy.

Experiment Method:

The ECG represents a graphic recording of the electrical cardiac activity traced on the electrocardiograph paper.[8].Proposed work is based on ECG signal using time domain Analysis The conventional ECG machine consists of 12 leads divided into two groups, i.e., limb leads and precordial leads. Limb leads are further categorized as standard bipolar limb leads (I, II, and III) and augmented unipolar leads (aVL, aVF, and aVR). The precordial leads include V1 to V6. The limb leads view the heart in a vertical plane, and the precordial leads record the heart's electrical activity in the horizontal plane.

Result and Discussion:

Time domain features will be explored to analyze the periodic functioning of the heart, in their health status shown in figure1.

Figure 1: Sample of ECG recorded

Figure 1. show signal from the time Domain Analysis Pr interval 166ms QRS duration 92ms Qt 352ms Qtc 416ms .The image displays a medical report containing an abnormal ECG result. The analysis indicates: Heart Rate (HR): 84 bpm, PR Interval: 166 ms QRS Duration : 92ms QT/QTc: 352/416 ms.

Conclusion:

Signal ECG is using time domain of Heart rate sinus rhythm was Abnormal.

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